

Prograde and retrograde stars in nuclear cluster mergers

Evolution of the supermassive black hole binary and the host galactic nucleus

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ABSTRACT

Context. Nuclear cluster mergers, involving the fusion of dense stellar clusters near the centres of galaxies, play a pivotal role in shaping galactic structures. The distribution of stellar orbits has significant effects on the formation and characteristics of Extreme Mass Ratio Inspirals (EMRIs).

Aims. In this study, we address the orbital distribution of stars in merging Nuclear Star Clusters (NSCs) and the subsequent effects on Supermassive Black Hole Binary (SMBHB) evolution.

Methods. We run dedicated direct-summation N -body simulations with different initial conditions to do a detailed study of the resulting NSC after their progenitors have merged.

Results. Our findings reveal that prograde stars form a flattened structure, while retrograde stars have a more spherical distribution. The axial ratios of the prograde component vary based on the presence and mass ratio of the SMBHs. The fraction of prograde and retrograde stars depends on the merger orbital properties and the SMBH mass ratio. The interactions of retrograde stars with the SMBHB affect the eccentricity and separation evolution of the binary. Our analysis reveals a strong correlation between angular momentum and the eccentricity of the SMBH binary. This relationship could serve as a mean to infer information about the stellar dynamics surrounding the binary. We find that prograde orbits are particularly close to the binary of SMBHs, a promising fact in regarding EMRI production. Moreover, prograde and retrograde stars have different kinematic structures, with the prograde stars typically rotating faster than the retrograde ones. The line-of-sight velocity and velocity dispersion, as well as the velocity anisotropy of each NSC, depend on the initial merger orbital properties and SMBH mass ratios. The prograde and retrograde stars always show different behaviours.

Conclusions. The distribution of stellar orbits and the dynamical properties of each kinematic population can potentially be used as a way to tell apart the properties of the parent nuclei which led to present NSCs and has an important impact on expected rates of EMRIs, which will be detected by future gravitational wave observatories like the Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA).

Key words. Galaxies: supermassive black holes – Galaxies: nuclei – Galaxies: kinematics and dynamics – Galaxies: star clusters: general – Gravitational waves

Fig. B.1. Time evolution of the L_z component of the angular momentum of the system, with respect to the density centre (top left panel). Time evolution of the eccentricity (bottom left panel) and energy (top right panel) of the SMBHB. Time evolution of the fraction of retrograde stars of the system, with respect to its centre of density (bottom left panel). The magenta cross marks the moment when the binding energy of the two supermassive black holes (SMBHs) becomes negative, i.e. the SMBHB formation time. All plots are related to M1.

Appendix B: Angular Momentum, Retrograde Stars, and Binary Eccentricity

In this Appendix, we provide plots showing the time evolution of the L_z component of the angular momentum of the system with respect to the density centre of the merging system. We also present the time evolution of the eccentricity and energy of the system composed of the two SMBHs. Additionally, we show the time evolution of the fraction of retrograde stars in the system. The plots are displayed for all the models with two SMBHs (Figures B1-B5). For models with one or no SMBHs, we provide plots showing the time evolution of L_z and the fraction of retrograde stars (Fig. B6). The interpretation of these plots is discussed in the main text.

Appendix C: Velocity maps of the final nuclear star clusters

In this Appendix, we present the velocity maps of all the final NSCs that we produce in our models. The maps are obtained using the Voronoi binning procedure presented by Cappellari & Copin (2003). To produce the maps, we adopt a fixed signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 15 in each bin, to ensure the homogeneity and reliability of the results. Fig. C1 shows the maps for models M1 to M4 and Fig. C2 shows the maps for models M5 to M7.

References

Cappellari, M. & Copin, Y. 2003, MNRAS, 342, 345

Fig. B.2. As in Fig. B.1, but for M2.

Fig. B.3. As in Fig. B.1, but for M3.

Fig. B.4. As in Fig. B.1, but for M4.

Fig. B.5. As in Fig. B.1, but for M5.

Fig. B.6. Time evolution of the L_z component of the angular momentum of the system, with respect to the density centre (top left panel for M6 and top right panel for M7). Time evolution of the fraction of retrograde stars of the system, with respect to its centre of density (bottom left panel for M6 and bottom right panel for M7).

Fig. C.1. Velocity maps for models M1 to M4. Each line represents a model. The left columns are for the entire NSC, the middle columns are for the prograde component and the right columns are for the retrograde component.

Fig. C.2. The same as Fig. C.1 but for models M5 to M7.